

**CONUS XICOI, A NEW SPECIES FROM ANGOLA
(PROSOBRANCHIA: CONIDAE)**

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In 1982, RÖCKEL & FERNANDES (:5) published a photograph showing three specimens of a *Conus* population from northern Angola and misidentified them with *C. lugubris* Reeve, 1849. But in the meantime thorough examinations of the type material of *C. lugubris* in BM (NH) unequivocally proved it to be a species from the Cape Verde Islands (ROLAN, in press) as already stated by COOMANS et al. in 1980. KIENER's illustration of *C. hieroglyphicus* «Duclos» (pl. 73, fig. 1a) seems probably based on specimens of this northern Angolan population instead of figuring the true *C. hieroglyphus* Duclos from the Caribbean (TROVÃO, 1978 and COOMANS et al. 1979 however identified KIENER's drawings with *C. albuquerquei* Trovão, 1978 — a standpoint we do not share).

Obviously by a printer's error the name «*hieroglyphus*» has been changed to «*hieroglyphicus*» in the plate. This name cannot be applied according to Art. 33 (c) of the ICZN. Thus the mentioned Angolan *Conus* population remained unnamed until now and therefore the following taxon is proposed.

Conus xicoi n. sp.

Description:

Shell: Stout and small (average adult size: 22-32mm); shape conical; length: width ratio is 1.6 — 1.7 Sides of last whorl convex posterior part but somewhat incurved towards the base. Body whorl nearly smooth except for 7-9 raised spiral cords above base, usually being very distinct; surface of good gloss with numerous densely spaced wrinkled spiral threads crossed by numerous close set axial threads. Shoulder angled and flat to slightly concave at top. Spire moderate with straight to slightly convex sides. Teleoconch consists of 8 complete whorls what mostly will be concealed on account of erosion. Tops of whorls flat with numerous finest close-set narrow spiral grooves crossed by axial threads. First 4-5 postnuclear whorls with 2 stronger spiral grooves, perceptible at juvenile specimens only. Background color of body whorl whitish grey tinted with two broad spiral zones of blue only leaving a narrow spiral ground-color band below midbody (width: \leq 1 mm). Dark reddish brown pattern composed of axially arranged irregular blotches and flammules, broad ziczac lines as well as fine axial lines and dashes. Amount of pattern elements variable; appearance of shell may be dominated by its dark pattern ele-

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ments largely overlaying background as well as by its light blue zones covered with a more or less reduced pattern. Shoulder and spire whitish blue with dark reddish brown axial streaks and blotches that may fuse together spirally to some extent. Inside margin of outer lip light and followed by a broader dark brown zone, color changing to light violet deeper within; narrow light spiral bands below shoulder and middle are very distinct.

Periostracum yellowish, relatively thick, and only partially translucent, with slightly tufted spiral lines.

Animal: Color cream pinkish; border of mantle dark pinkish covered with dark dots; siphon and proboscis blackish. Number of radular teeth varies from 48 to 52, length of teeth is about 0.56 mm; serration comprises 22 to 27 denticles and length ratio of shell: tooth ranges between 44 : 1 and 56 : 1 (based upon 3 specimens examined measuring 31.3 x 19.5 mm, 25.3 x 16.3 mm, 17.8 x 10.4mm).

Habitat: *C. xicoi* occurs intertidally from very low water down to the surge zone. It lives in rock crevices or sometimes between rocks, partly buried in sand.

Range: Known from Santiago Beach (30 km north of Luanda) up to the mouth of the Dande river, Angola.

Type locality: Santiago Beach (30 km north of Luanda), Angola.

Type material: Holotype (25.5 x 14.7 mm) in Senckenberg-Museum Frankfurt. Paratypes: Muséum National d'Hist. Nat. Paris, 2 paratypes (29.4 x 18.5 mm and 27.5 x 18 mm). British Museum (Natural History), 2 paratypes (30.3 x 19.8 mm and 17.4 x 9.9 mm). Institute of Malacology Tokyo, 2 paratypes (30.1 x 18.7 and 17.9 x 10.6 mm). American Museum of Natural History, New York, 2 paratypes (25.8 x 16.1 and 21.7 x 12.8 mm). Centro de Zoologia, Lisboa, 2 paratypes (30.5 x 19.3 and 27.9 x 17 mm). Francisco Fernandes, 12 paratypes (max. size 31.3 x 19.7). Dieter Röckel, 8 paratypes (max. size 30.1 x 19.7 mm). António Monteiro, 2 paratypes (max. size 23.6 x 14 mm). Ilidio Felix Alves, 2 Paratypes (27.9 x 18.3 mm and 22.8 x 14.4 mm). Joao Messias, 2 paratypes (27.9 x 17.4 and 17.2 x 10.7 mm). Herculano Trovao, 2 paratypes (25.2 x 16.4 and 17.6 x 10.5 mm). Werner Korn: 1 paratype (21.7 x 12.8 mm). Emilio Rolán, 3 paratypes (max. size 28.8 x 17.3 mm). Amarilio Ramalho 1 paratype (24 x 14.7 mm).

Etymology: Named in honour of Francisco («Xico») Fernandes from Luanda, who has been the first collecting specimens of the n. sp.

Discussion: All endemic *Conus* species from southern Angola (e.g. *Conus bulbosus* Reeve, *C. variegatus* Kiener, *C. africanus* Kiener and numerous related species) differ from *C. xicoi* by their rounded shoulder which is **convex** at top. In color pattern *C. xicoi* rather resembles *C. aemulus* Reeve. But the latter one differs by its larger average adult size (< 50 mm), by its more slender shape (length: width ratio about 1.85), and by the presence of dotted or dashed spiral lines in its body pattern. Similar looking species from the Cape Verde Islands, in particular *Conus cuneolus* Reeve and *Conus lugubris* Reeve, differ by having 2-3 distinct spiral grooves on top of whorls.

Acknowledgement: I express my gratitude to Dr. Emilio Rolan for preparing a description of the radula tooth and for his excellent drawing of the tooth.

SUMMARY

Conus xicoi n. sp. is described from the littoral of northern Angola. The new species is compared with endemic species from southern Angola, with *Conus aemulus* Reeve and with *Conus cuneolus* Reeve and *C. lugubris* Reeve from Cape Verde Islands.

RESUMO

O autor descreve o *Conus xicoi* como uma nova espécie do norte de Angola. Difere das espécies endêmicas do sul de Angola, como o *C. bulbosus* Reeve ou o *C. variegatus* Kiener, em primeiro lugar pelo ombro anguloso, a parte superior da última volta ligeiramente côncava e a presença de sulcos espirais nas primeiras 4-5 voltas pós-nucleares. O *Conus aemulus* Reeve, que também vive no norte de Angola (em águas tranquilas, geralmente em baías protegidas) é muito maior, mais esguio e com um padrão diferente; espécies de aspecto similar das ilhas de Cabo Verde diferem por terem 2-3 sulcos espirais em todas as voltas da espira, bem como pelo padrão distinto.

LITERATURE CITED

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A

B

C

D

- A — *Conus xicoi* n. sp. Holotype (25,5 × 15,7mm)
- B — *Conus xicoi* n. sp. Holotype (25,5 × 15,7mm)
- C — *Conus xicoi* n. sp. Dark form (23,3 × 14mm)
- D — *Conus xicoi* n. sp. Dark form (23,3 × 14mm)

A

B

C

D

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- A — Profile of shoulder - *Conus xicoi* n. sp.
- B — Profile of shoulder - *Conus bulbus*
- C — *Conus xicoi* n. sp. specimen with periostracum.
- D — *Conus aemulus* Reeve (44,6 × 24,5mm)